

The Effect of Acute Creatine Supplementation on Physiological Variables of Continuous and Intermittent Soccer Activities of Men Soccer Players

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Abstract : The aim of this study was studying the effect of acute creatine supplementation on physiological variables of continuous and intermittent soccer activities of men soccer players. 32 soccer players from Tarbiat Moalem University aged (22/3+-1/6) volunteered for this research and were divided into two groups randomly. Both experimental and control groups after 6 days taking supplementation were tested. For measuring height and weight meter and balance were used. Questionnaire for health background, lactate electro, heart beat measuring polar electro, continuous and intermittent training program and time recorder were used for data collection. For data analysis descriptive statistical techniques, two-way ANOVA and F test were used. The result of this study showed increased significantly in heart rate in control group. For control group heart beat was (71/6 +- 3/5) and for experimental group it was (75/3 +- 4/9). No significant differences were observed in players weight after taking creatine.

Keywords : heartbeat, lactate Blood, creatine, soccer players of Tarbiat Moalem University

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